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A potential role for EYA2/EYA3 phosphatase in compensatory regulation following inhibition of ERBB2 growth factor signaling.

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We studied total transcription in cells with ERBB2 inhibition to discover genes without bias that engage in compensatory or rebound signaling associated with resistance to clinical interventions. We found activation of phosphatases EYA2 and EYA3 in the context of HER2 inhibition. We recently described evidence demonstrating STK16 activation in compensatory signaling in cancer cells exposed to a growth factor inhibitor. Relative contributions to resistant behavior and redundancy are not yet understood.